

Supplementary Materials

Figure S1. Confirmation of AsPC-1 tumor metastases by histology. (A) Primary AsPC-1 tumor in pancreas of scrambled siRNA NP-treated control mouse. (B) AsPC-1 tumor is shown metastasized to the abdominal wall in a gastrin siRNA NP-treated mouse. (C) AsPC-1 tumor metastases confirmed in the

liver (arrows) of a mouse treated with mutant Kras siRNA NPs. **(D)** AsPC-1 tumor metastases confirmed invading the stomach (arrows) of a mouse treated with mutant Kras siRNA NPs. **(E)** Metastases of AsPC-1 tumor cells in the spleen of a scrambled siRNA NP treated mouse. **(F)** Lymph node invasion with the AsPC-1 tumor of a PBS-treated mouse.

Intestine

Figure S2. Mouse intestine. H&E imaged at low magnification (4X, top row; scale bar 500 μ m) and higher magnification (10X, bottom row; scale bar 200 μ m) if intestine sections from untreated (control), scrambled NP-treated, or muKRAS NP-treated revealed normal histology and no inflammation.

Stomach

Figure S3. Mouse stomach. H&E imaged at low magnification (4X, top row; scale bar 500 μ m) and higher magnification (10X, bottom row; scale bar 200 μ m) of stomach sections from untreated (control), scrambled NP treated, or muKRAS NP-treated revealed normal histology and no inflammation.

Liver

Figure S4. Mouse liver. H&E imaged at low magnification (4X, top row; scale bar 500 μ m) and higher magnification (10X, bottom row; scale bar 200 μ m) of liver sections from untreated (control), scrambled NP treated, or muKRAS NP-treated revealed normal histology and no inflammation.

Kidney

Figure S5. Mouse kidney. H&E imaged at low magnification (4X, top row; scale bar 500 μ m) and higher magnification (10X, bottom row; scale bar 200 μ m) of kidney sections from untreated (control), scrambled NP treated, or muKRAS NP-treated revealed normal histology and no inflammation.

Spleen

Figure S6. Mouse spleen. H&E imaged at low magnification (4X, top row; scale bar 500 μ m) and higher magnification (10X, bottom row; scale bar 200 μ m) of spleen sections from untreated (control), scrambled NP treated, or muKRAS NP-treated revealed normal histology and no inflammation.

Supplementary Table S1: Sequences of the siRNAs loaded to nanoparticles

siRNA	Sense 5' to 3'	Anti-sense 5' to 3'	Molecular weight, g/mol
Wild type <i>Kras</i> *	GUUGGAGCUG GGUGG CGUAGTT	CUACGCC ACC AGCUCCA ACTT	13,447.2
Mutant, <i>Kras</i> <i>/KRAS</i> *	GUUGGAGCUG GAUGG CGUAGTT	CUACGCC AUC AGCUCCA ACTT	13,348.2
Scrambled Control	CGAAGUGUGUGUGUGUGGCTT	GCCACACACACACACUUCGTT	13,371.2
Gastrin (<i>GAST</i>)	GUGCUGAGGAUGAGAACUA	TAGTTCTCATCCTCAGC	11262.2

*Bold codon in the *Kras* sequence refers to the G12D mutation

Supplementary Table S2: Primers used for qRT-PCR.

Primer name	Forward 5'-3'	Reverse 5—3'
Mouse Mutant Kras*	GAT GGCGTAGGCAAGAGC	GCACGCAGACTGTAGAGCAG
Mouse Wild-type Kras	TGGTGGCGTAGGCAAGAG	GCAGACTGTAGAGCAGCGTTA
Mouse Wild-type Kras	TTGGAGCTGGTGGCGTAG	TAGAGCAGCGTTACCTCTATCG
Mouse HPRT	TCAGTCAACGGGGGACATAAA	GGGGCTGTACTGCTTAACCAG
Human Mutant KRAS	CTTGTGGTAGTTGGAGCTGATG	TGTTGGATCATATTCGTCCACAA
Human Wild-type KRAS	TGTGGTAGTTGGAGCTGGT	ATTGTTGGATCATATTCGTCCAC
Human gastrin	GCCTCTCATCATCGAAGGCA	GCCGAAGTCCATCCATCCAT
Human GAPDH	GTCTCCTCTGACTTCAACAGCG	ACCACCCTCTTGCTGTAGCCAA

*Bold codon for prier is able to differentiate wild type from mutant Kras